

Investigating the Relationship between Case Marking and Word Order in Languages:

A Cross-Linguistic Analysis using WALS Data

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1. Introduction

The relationship between case marking and word order in languages has been a topic of extensive research in linguistics. Different languages employ various strategies to indicate grammatical roles and establish word order patterns. While the specific relationship between case marking and word order can vary across languages, there are some general tendencies that have been observed.

According to Dryer (2013), in Subject-Object-Verb (SOV) languages, “case markers often function as the primary means of indicating grammatical relations”. On the other hand, languages with a Subject-Verb-Object (SVO) word order tend to rely less on case marking and instead employ word order as the primary means of indicating grammatical relations. In SVO languages, the subject typically appears before the verb, and the object follows the verb. According to Lehmann (2015), “SVO languages have a relatively fixed word order and rely on position rather than marking to indicate grammatical relations”.

Greenberg’s influential work on linguistic universals (1963) identified correlations between word order and case marking. He proposed the famous Greenberg’s Universals, which include statements such as “If a language has dominant SOV word order, it is always postpositional.” This finding suggests a strong connection between case marking and word order, supporting the hypothesis that certain word order patterns are associated with specific types of case marking systems.

Furthermore, studies on specific language families have shed light on the relationship between case marking and word order. For instance, research on Indo-European languages, such as Latin and German, has explored how case markings contribute to the flexibility or rigidity of word order in these languages (Whitman 2008). Similar investigations have been conducted on other language families, including Finno-Ugric languages (Vilkuna 1989) and Austronesian languages (Chung 1998).

By building upon the earlier literature, the current research expands our understanding of language universals and typological tendencies. The study described in the text utilizes large datasets from the World Atlas of Language Structures Online (WALS) to analyze the relationship between case marking and word order in a broader cross-linguistic context. By employing statistical techniques such as Pearson’s Chi-squared test, the research aims to address the following research question: Is there a discernible correlation between case marking and word order across diverse languages? The hypothesis posits that case marking plays a pivotal role in indicating the grammatical function of nouns in

verb-ending languages. The datasets utilized are sourced from The World Atlas of Language Structures Online (WALS), specifically Chapter 49 on the Number of Cases and Chapter 81 on the Order of Subject, Object, and Verb.

2. Methods and Tools

To investigate the correlation between the number of cases and word order, Pearson’s Chi-squared test will be employed using R Studio. Additionally, visual representations of world maps depicting the number of cases and word order will be generated using Tableau.

To process the downloaded datasets and calculate the correlation between the number of cases and word order, preprocessing is necessary. A macroarea for each language is determined by cross-referencing WALS codes and information from another dataset called “languoid.” The number of cases dataset comprises 261 entries, while the word order dataset encompasses 1,377 entries. These two datasets are merged, resulting in a combined file with 1,398 entries. To establish a correlation between the two variables, the descriptions need to be converted into numerical codes.

For the number of cases, the descriptions are assigned codes based on Sinnemäki’s (2020) classification:

A number of Cases	Code
No morphological case-marking	0
2 cases	2
3 cases	3
4 cases	4
5 cases	5
6-7 cases	6
8-9 cases	7
10 or more cases	8
Exclusively borderline case-marking	0

Table 1: Codes for a number of cases

Regarding word order, codes are assigned based on the assumption that languages with verb-final word order, where both nominal arguments precede the main lexical verb, tend to develop complex case systems more frequently than languages with SVO word order (Sinnemäki, 2020). Consequently, word order is divided into three groups. The first group comprises SVO and is assigned the number 1. The second group encompasses verb-final word orders (OSV and SOV) and is assigned the number 2. The final group includes the remaining orders (no dominant word order, OVS, VOS, and VSO) and is assigned the number 0.

Word Order	Code
SVO	1
OSV	2
SOV	2
No dominant order	0
OVS	0
VOS	0
VSO	0

Table 2: Codes for word order

The contingency table presented below is utilized to conduct Pearson's Chi-squared test. For the purpose of our research, the third group assigned the number 0 is disregarded, leaving only two variables: verb-final and SVO.

A Number of Cases / Word Order	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Verb-final	31	0	11	5	3	4	22	16	9
SVO	52	0	5	1	3	2	4	0	0

Table 3: Contingency Table

Since some cells contain zero frequencies, which can lead to complications when calculating test statistics and p-values, two solutions have been proposed. The first solution involves changing 0 to 0.01, while the second solution categorizes the number of cases as simple (≤ 2) and complex (> 2), excluding values like #N/A or 99 indicating a lack of information. Although these methods yield slightly different results, they align in the same direction.

To visualize the datasets in a world map, information of longitude and latitude is used in Tableau. The variables “a number of cases” and “word order” are assigned to different colors on the map. A lighter color represents a smaller number of cases while a darker color represents a larger number of cases. Green color is assigned to “Exclusively borderline case marking” and pink to “No morphological case marking.” In word order, the variables are grouped into two groups: OSV&SOV, which represents verb-ending languages, and SVO.

3. Results

3.1. A Number of Cases

The overview of a number of cases obtained from WALS is illustrated in the charts and the table below.

Chart 1: A distribution of a number of cases in the world

(https://public.tableau.com/views/LanguageTypologyCases/ANumberOfCases?:language=en-US&:display_count=n&:origin=viz_share_link)

A NUmber of Cases	Macro Areas					Grand Total	
	Eurasia	North America	Papunesi a	South Africa	Australi a		
No morphological case-marking	18	17	31	23	9	2	100
2 cases	10	4	1	4	4		23
3 cases	4	2		2	1		9
4 cases	5	1	1	2			9
5 cases	6	1	1		3	1	12
6-7 cases	14	7	2	7	5	2	37
8-9 cases	10	3	3		2	5	23
10 or more cases	15	1	1		2	5	24
Exclusively borderline case-marking	1	9	4	3	6	1	24
Grand Total	83	45	44	41	32	16	261

Table 4: Distribution of a number of cases in each macro area

Chart 2: A distribution of a number of cases in each macro area in a bar chart

3.2. Word Order

The overview of word order obtained from WALS is illustrated in the charts and the table below.

Chart 3: A distribution of word order in the world

(https://public.tableau.com/views/LanguageTypologyCasesandWordOrder/WordOrder?:language=en-US&:display_count=n&:origin=viz_share_link)

Word Order	Macro Area						Grand Total
	Africa	Australia	Eurasia	North America	Papunesia	South America	
SVO	244	13	76	16	115	24	488
OSV	1	1			1	1	4
SOV	62	34	195	61	145	67	564
No dominant order	32	43	17	55	21	21	189
OVS	1	2			1	7	11
VOS	1	2	1	8	9	4	25
VSO	22		6	36	26	5	95
Grand Total	363	95	295	176	318	129	1376

Table 5: Distribution of word order in each macro area

Chart 4: A distribution of word order in each macro area in a bar chart

3.3. Merged

The chart and the table below demonstrate the merged dataset of a number of cases and word order obtained from WALS.

Word Order	A Number of Cases									Grand #N/A	Grand Total
	No morphological case-marking	2	3	4	5	6-7	8-9	10 or more	Exclusively borderline case-marking		
No dominant order	11	1	3	2	2	4	3	6	5	152	189
OSV										4	4
OVS	2						2		1	6	11
SOV	18	11	5	3	4	22	16	9	13	463	564
SVO	50	5	1	3	2	4		4	2	417	488
VOS	6	1							1	17	25
VSO	10	3		1		3				78	95
#N/A	3	2			4	4	2	5	2		22
Grand Total	100	23	9	9	12	37	23	24	24	1137	1398

Table 6: A number of cases and word order

Chart 5: A number of cases and word order in a bar chart

4. Analysis

The analysis presents two solutions to address the issue of zero values in the contingency table. The first solution involves changing the zeros to 0.01, while the second solution categorizes the number of cases into a simple and complex case marking system.

4.1. Method 1: Change 0 to 0.01

A Number of Cases / Word Order	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Verb-final	31	0.01	11	5	3	4	22	16	9
SVO	52	0.01	5	1	3	2	4	0.01	0.01

Table 7: Adjusted contingency table with the value of 0.01

This method yields a test statistic (X-squared) of 43.2 with 8 degrees of freedom (df). The corresponding p-value is 0.0000008054, indicating a highly significant result.

4.2. Method 2: Simple and Complex Cases

A Number of Cases / Word Order	Complex Cases	Simple Cases
Verb-final	59	42
SVO	10	57

Table 8: Adjusted contingency table with the new categorization of case marking system

In the second contingency table, Yates' continuity correction (Yates 1934) is applied due to the small sample size. Yates' continuity correction adjusts the chi-squared test statistic to account for the discreteness of the observed frequencies. It involves subtracting 0.5 from the absolute difference between each observed frequency and its expected frequency before squaring the differences and summing them to calculate the chi-squared test statistic.

The second method yields a test statistic (X-squared) of 29.707 with 1 degree of freedom (df). The associated p-value is 0.0000005026.

5. Summary and Discussions

Both results obtained from Pearson's Chi-squared test indicate a significant association between the number of cases and word order. Consequently, the null hypothesis, which assumes no association between the variables, can be rejected. The small p-values provide strong evidence supporting a significant association between the number of cases and word order. This observation implies that the presence of a complex case marking system is associated with the presence of flexible word order. Conversely, in Subject-Verb-Object (SVO) languages, word order is more fixed, and case marking plays a relatively smaller role. This observation suggests that a simpler case marking system is associated with a more fixed word order.

These findings also confirm Greenberg's Universals, which states that if a language has a dominant SOV word order, it is always postpositional. This finding implies that the presence of a postpositional case marking system is associated with the presence of an SOV word order. Similarly, the research indicates that languages with verb-final word orders tend to develop complex case systems more frequently.

There are several caveats, areas of improvement, and future work aspects that can be considered. While WALS is a valuable resource, it is important to acknowledge the criteria used to obtain the values of features. For example, in Chapter 49 A Number of Cases (Iggesen 2013), the author takes into account only morphological cases on nominals, which may not provide a complete picture of the syntactic or semantic functions of cases within a given language as Bickel and Zariquiey stated in 2017. Arppe and Haagsma (2018) also mentioned "A purely morphological approach may overlook the nuances of case usage in different languages." As seen in Table 4 and Chart 2, this method puts many languages in the category of "No morphological case marking" (100 out of 261).

Future work could explore the interplay between case marking and other linguistic phenomena, such as agreement systems, morphological complexity, or syntactic structures, to gain a more comprehensive understanding of language typological patterns. More research could be conducted to investigate the impact of language contact and historical processes on the relationship between case marking and word order, providing insights into language change and evolution.

6. References

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Appendix

R Code

- Preprocess the data.

```
# Subset for verb-final word order (num_WO = 2)
verb_final <- merged[merged$num_WO == 2, ]

# Subset for SVO word order (num_WO = 1)
svo <- merged[merged$num_WO == 1, ]

# Create a vector of all possible number of cases (0 to 8)
num_cases <- 0:8

# Calculate the frequency of each number of cases for verb-final word order
verb_final_case_counts <- table(factor(verb_final$num_case, levels = num_cases))

# Calculate the frequency of each number of cases for SVO word order
svo_case_counts <- table(factor(svo$num_case, levels = num_cases))

# Create a contingency table
contingency_table <- matrix(c(verb_final_case_counts, svo_case_counts),
                           nrow = 2, byrow = TRUE,
                           dimnames = list(c("Verb-final", "SVO"),
                                           c("0", "1", "2", "3", "4", "5", "6", "7", "8")))

# Perform a chi-squared test
chi_square_test <- chisq.test(contingency_table)

# Print the chi-squared test results
print(chi_square_test)
```

- Problems

There are the values of 0 in the table which leads to error in calculation.

- Solution 1

The first solution is to replace 0 with 0.01. We manually create a new contingency with the substitutions of 0.

```

# Create the contingency table
contingency_table_1 <- matrix(c(31, 0.01, 11, 5, 3, 4, 22, 16, 9, 52, 0, 5, 1, 3, 2, 4, 0.01, 0.01),
                             nrow = 2, byrow = TRUE,
                             dimnames = list(c("Verb-final", "SVO"),
                                             c("0.01", "1", "2", "3", "4", "5", "6", "7", "8")))

# Perform Pearson's chi-squared test
chi_square_test_1 <- chisq.test(contingency_table_1)

# Print the chi-squared test results
print(chi_square_test_1)

```

- Solution 2

The second solution is to group cases into simple and complex cases.

```

# Filter out unwanted values for simple cases
verb_final_simple_cases <- sum(verb_final$num_case >= 0 & verb_final$num_case <= 2)
svo_simple_cases <- sum(svo$num_case >= 0 & svo$num_case <= 2)

# Filter out unwanted values for complex cases
verb_final_complex_cases <- sum(verb_final$num_case >= 3 & verb_final$num_case <= 8)
svo_complex_cases <- sum(svo$num_case >= 3 & svo$num_case <= 8)

# Create a contingency table
contingency_table_0 <- matrix(c(verb_final_complex_cases, verb_final_simple_cases,
                                svo_complex_cases, svo_simple_cases),
                             nrow = 2, byrow = TRUE,
                             dimnames = list(c("Verb-final", "SVO"),
                                             c("Complex Cases", "Simple Cases")))

# Perform a chi-squared test with Yates' continuity correction
chi_square_test_0 <- chisq.test(contingency_table_0, correct = TRUE)

# Print the chi-squared test results
print(chi_square_test_0)

```

The results are similar.